

Wireless body area networks: A critical review of the state-of-the-art security schemes

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Abstract

The continued advancement of information communication technologies (ICT) has led to the adoption of internet of things in the healthcare sector. One of such application domain of ICT is the wireless body area network (WBAN), which enables remote monitoring of vital biomedical parameters on the patient or the elderly. Upon collection of these parameters, they are forwarded to the remote hospital servers where analysis and appropriate actions are taken. Obviously, the data exchanged in these networks is sensitive and private and hence can have devastating effects on the patient if leaked to the unintended parties. Consequently, many security solutions have been developed in literature. The goal of this paper is to carry out an extensive review of these security schemes in an effort to pin point their strengths and weaknesses. Based on the findings, it is evident that many of these security solutions try to attain a number of security and privacy protection. However, it is noted that these schemes still lack many of the required security goals such as anonymity, untraeability, forward key secrecy as well as resistance to many of the conventional attacks. Therefore, some recommendations for the attainment of perfect privacy and security are given towards the end of this paper.

Keywords: Security; Privacy; WBAN; Attacks; LoT; Sensors

1. Introduction

The ever increasing utilization of mobile devices, wireless sensor networks (WSNs), internet of things (IoT) and sensors has seen the healthcare sector adopting IoT devices to collect data, monitor patients and communicate with patients over wireless body area networks (WBANs) [1]. In essence, WBAN is a collection of smart medical sensors that are implanted in the patient body or placed around the patient. As shown in Figure 1, the main components of a typical WBAN include the medical staff, sensors and gateway nodes.

These sensors offer real-time monitoring and healthcare support to the patients. They may also be utilized to monitor the elderly people who need some permanent care devoid of being hospitalized. In such a scenario, the monitoring is done at home using sensors that then send the collected data to the hospital using some wireless transmission channels. In case of emergencies such as heart attack, the medical staff can initiate some immediate actions without further delays. In terms of computational capabilities, gateway nodes are more powerful than sensors and they act secure interfaces between the medical staff and the sensors.

As explained in [2], WBANs collect patient health information and forward the same to medical staff so as to monitor and control the patient's health remotely. As such, it makes it possible for patients to be diagnosed using some remote clinical nano-sensors [3]. The collected data may include body temperature, ECG, sugar level and blood pressure among

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others [4]. WBAN presents an emerging domain that employs ubiquitous technologies such as smart sensors [5], cloud computing, embedded systems and wireless network technologies to boost the electronic-health care system [6]. As explained in [7]-[12], WBAN based systems represent one of the most critical technologies in the biomedical field. Basically, important patient and elderly health parameters and movements are perceived and forwarded to the healthcare service provider for analysis and appropriate action [2], [13]. As a result of the effectiveness and demand for WBAN, a new International communication standard IEEE 802.15.6 [14] has been developed.

Figure 1 WBAN Communication Architecture

In spite of the numerous merits that this technology has come with, the open nature of the wireless communication channels coupled with cloud computing introduce a number of security threats and vulnerabilities [15]. As such, the privacy and integrity of the exchanged data may be compromised [16], [17]. For instance, an attacker can eavesdrop, intercept, modify, or replay the exchanged messages. In addition, the data stored in the utilized mobile devices and sensors can be retrieved. As explained in [1], attacks such as offline password guessing, privileged insider, user tracking, session key disclosure, forgery and impersonations are possible in WBANs. Since the exchanged data directly impacts on patient health and life, its confidentiality should be upheld [18]. The resource-constrained nature [19] of the devices involved in WBAN is another major issue. Although cloud computing can offload some of the processing of these devices, it introduces numerous threats and vulnerabilities that can be exploited by adversaries [20]. One way of dealing with these challenges is through data encryption [21]. This is particularly important for inter WBAN which uses internet links to connect the patient to the medical servers [22], [23].

In light of the above challenges, there is need for the development of lightweight and efficient security solutions for these networks to curb the numerous active and passive attacks [1], [3], [24], [25], [26], [27]. One of the most effective mechanisms for boosting security in wireless networks is through strong mutual authentication [28], [29]. This will go a long way in insuring that only legitimate healthcare personnel has access to the highly sensitive and confidential patient data [52]. The main contributions of this article are as follows:

- An extensive review of the current techniques for achieving security and privacy in wireless body area networks is provided.
- The challenges and strengths of the security solutions designed for wireless body area networks are identified.
- Based on the shortcomings identified in literature, recommendations for attaining perfect security and privacy are provided

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 discusses related work while Section 3 presents the obtained results. On the other hand, Section 4 offers the recommendations emanating from this study while Section 5 concludes the paper.

2. Related work

Many security solutions have been put forward by researchers in the industry as well as academia in an effort to protect WBAN communication process. However, majority of these techniques still have security holes, while others have high complexities in terms of storage, computation and communication. For example, the authentication protocols in [30] are lightweight and incur less communication overheads but are never evaluated from the privacy and security perspectives. On the other hand, the two-factor authentication scheme in [31] cannot uphold user anonymity [19]. These issues can be addressed by the secure and efficient approaches in [32] and [33]. Using offline signatures, a remote authentication scheme is developed in [34]. However, this scheme is not suitable for high mobility and multiple server

environments. Although the protocol in [35] potentially addresses this issue, it is susceptible to denial of service attack [36]. Therefore, the smart card and proximity-based authentication schemes are introduced in [37] and [38] respectively to curb this attack. To further enhance security, multi-hop channel and AES based authentication protocols are presented in [39] and [40] respectively. On the other hand, a risk-based adaptive authentication framework is developed in [41]. However, validation [42] of the proposed framework is missing.

Using the physical unclonable functions (PUFs), lightweight protocols are developed in [43]-[47]. Unfortunately, the security analysis of the scheme in [46] is missing. In addition, PUF-based schemes have stability challenges [48]. Further, the protocol in [44] is vulnerable to denial of service attacks and cannot uphold perfect forward secrecy [49] nor can it ensure session key agreement. To prevent this attack, an energy-efficient authentication and key agreement protocol is developed in [50]. Although the technique incurs less communication, memory and computation overheads [51], it cannot withstand many security attacks [52]. To address this challenge, many schemes have been put forward in [53]-[58]. However, most of these schemes are not lightweight [59] and cannot offer forward secrecy, untraceability as well as resilience against key compromise and impersonation attacks [1], [60]. For instance, the scheme [57] incurs extremely high communication costs. To reduce the computation and communication overheads, a secure anonymous user authentication scheme is developed in [61]. Similarly, an efficient and privacy preserving smart card based authentication protocol is presented in [62]. However, this approach is vulnerable to offline password guessing, replay, smart card loss and forgery attacks. Similarly, the scheme in [63] is susceptible to key compromise, replay, privacy leakages and impersonation attacks [6].

To minimize computation and storage complexities, an ECG-based authentication scheme is introduced in [64]. However, this protocol lacks protection against Sybil, sink and wormhole attacks. To prevent these attacks, an identity-based anonymous authentication is developed in [19]. Although this approach offers mutual authentication, key agreement and user anonymity, identity-based schemes have key escrow problems [65]. The protocol in [66] can help address this issue, but it incurs high execution time at the server side. The schemes in [67] and [68] are fairly lightweight and hence can address the performance issues in [66]. Unfortunately, the approach in [68] lacks security evaluation against adversarial attacks [52]. Based on user's password, an authentication technique is developed in [69]. Unfortunately, low entropy passwords are vulnerable to brute force and dictionary attacks. Although the PUF based scheme in [70] is resilient energy-efficient, it is devoid of discussion on security features. On the other hand, a number of vulnerabilities have been discovered in [71] by the author in [72]. As such, a smart card-based secure authentication scheme has been introduced in [72] to eliminate these vulnerabilities. Unfortunately, this scheme lacks analysis of the communication and computation costs. In addition, it lacks formal verification [73] of the offered security features. To resolve sensor impersonation and server impersonation attacks in [74], energy efficient authentication schemes are developed in [75] and [76]. However, the protocol in [76] has some security loopholes [77]. The proximity-based authentication mechanism in [78] can potentially prevent some of these security setbacks.

Using elliptic curve cryptography (ECC) and bilinear pairing operations, an authentication protocol is developed in [79]. However, these pairing operations are computationally extensive [80] for the WBAN devices. To prevent denial of service, man-in-the-middle, session hijacking and impersonation attacks, a security protocol is introduced in [81]. However, this scheme has not been analytically analyzed and is limited to ECG features. On the other hand, high computation and client impersonation attacks have been identified in [82]. Therefore, an improved protocol has been presented in [83], which is shown to offer anonymity, mutual authentication and forward secrecy. In addition, it is robust against tampering, replay and impersonation attacks. To securely pair wearable devices, a proximity-based authentication technique is presented in [84], while three-factor mutual authentication scheme is presented in [85]. Although the protocol in [85] reduces communication and computation costs, it does not consider security features such as untraceability, unlinkability and non-repudiation. To improve on this, the schemes in [86] and [87] can be utilized. However, the protocol in [86] is vulnerable to de-synchronization [88] attacks. Therefore, enhanced two-factor authentication approaches are introduced in [89]-[91] based on smart cards and passwords.

Based on ECC and certificateless cryptography, a conditional privacy-preserving authentication protocol is developed in [92]. Although this technique prevents forgery attack and incurs less computation and communication overheads, batch verification is not included. To reduce these message exchanges, an identity-based authentication and key agreement protocol is developed in [93]. Unfortunately, this scheme cannot offer unlinkability and user anonymity [94]. Similarly, the technique in [95] lacks user anonymity and is vulnerable to smart card loss, offline password guessing and credentials leakage attacks. Consequently, an improved a biometric based distributed key management protocol is developed in [96]. This approach is shown to provide confidentiality, security, authentication and resilience against different attacks and threats. Although the retina-based authentication scheme in [97] is storage efficient, it lacks evaluation against security attacks. Similarly, anonymity preserving authentication scheme in [98] is efficient and offers conditional privacy but lacks discussion on vital security attacks such as man-in-the-middle, impersonation,

modification and eavesdropping. To address these issues, novel identity-based authentication protocols are developed in [99] and [100]. However, the deployed bilinear pairing operations render the scheme in [99] computationally intensive [101]. In addition, it is vulnerable to impersonation attack and does not offer mutual authentication [102]. On the other hand, the protocol in [100] lacks user anonymity [19]. Similarly, the two-factor authentication protocol in [103] is vulnerable to offline guessing attacks [1], while the protocol in [104] is susceptible to node compromise attack. To address some of these attacks, a privacy preserving certificateless scheme is introduced in [105]. Unfortunately, this scheme incurs high computation costs [106] and its resilience against security attacks is not provided. On the other hand, a pairing based authentication protocol is presented in [107]. However, this protocol cannot withstand impersonation attacks [108].

To mutually construct the session key, a lightweight authentication technique is presented in [109]. Unfortunately, this approach is vulnerable to user tracking and offline password guessing attacks. To solve these issues, a multi-hop and lightweight authentication schemes are presented in [110] and [111] respectively. Although the scheme in [111] offers untraceability, it presents some challenges in the management of a set of pseudo-IDs [112] and secret keys. Similarly, the protocols in [113] and [114] are not evaluated against security attacks. On the other hand, the approach in [115] offers security evaluation, where it is demonstrated to be robust against controller and sensor node spoofing attacks. To address the issues in [111], a novel user authentication protocol developed in [116] can be utilized. However, this scheme is susceptible to replay and spoofing attacks [117] and hence an improved scheme was put forward in [117]. Unfortunately, this scheme cannot withstand user forgery and offline password guessing attacks [118]. Similarly, the ECC based protocol in [119] cannot achieve user unlinkability [47]. Although the group device pairing protocol in [120] can potentially address this issue, it can be compromised by malicious group members [121]. This challenge is prevented by the protocol in [122], which is robust against eavesdropping, man-in-the-middle, jamming, impersonation, modification and replay attacks. Unfortunately, this protocol is never evaluated against non-repudiation. Similarly, the scheme in [123] is vulnerable to user tracking attacks [124]. Although the scheme in [125] provides conditional privacy and protection against forgery attacks, it remains susceptible to denial of service and impersonation attacks. On the other hand, the two-factor protocol in [126] offers untraceability but cannot resist session-specific temporary information threats and de-synchronization attacks [127]. It may also permit unauthorized logins. These challenges can be solved by the three factor authentication protocol developed in [128], based on passwords, smart cards and biometrics. Similarly, the protocol in [129] is efficient and offers strong forward secrecy as well as resilience against numerous attacks. As such, it can address the security issues in [126].

Chaotic cryptography has also been crucial in securing WBANs. For instance, a chaotic map based scheme is presented in [130]. This scheme is demonstrated to offer protection against information disclosure. On the other hand, a lightweight authentication protocol is presented in [131], which is shown to be energy-efficient, fast and requires less memory space during authentication procedures. As such, it can help address the inefficiency in the homomorphic encryption method developed in [132]. Although the one-to-many group authentication scheme in [133] helps establish a group key between the sensor and the PDA, it lacks resilience against key escrow [134] and non-repudiation. Similarly, the certificateless encryption and signature scheme in [135] offers scalable and anonymous remote authentication. It is also robust against chosen-plaintext attack. Unfortunately, its resilience against other attacks is not analyzed. On the other hand, authors in [136] have deployed asymmetric key generation approach for efficient and secure data transmission. However, the asymmetric key technique calls for pairs of public and private keys, which renders this algorithm slower and highly complex [137]. Similarly, in-field user authentication scheme in [138] lacks security analysis. As such, the three-phase authentication scheme in [139] and lightweight two-factor authentication scheme in [140] have been developed to offer and security analysis. In particular, the protocol in [140] is shown to be robust against session key disclosure, tracking and offline guessing attacks. However, it fails to offer forward key secrecy [1]. On the other hand an RSS based authentication scheme is presented in [141] while a certificate-less authentication protocol is developed in [142]. However, the scheme in [142] is vulnerable to impersonation attack [143] and cannot offer user anonymity [119].

To offer scalability at low computation overheads, a password-based user access control scheme is presented in [144]. Unfortunately, this approach fails to provide anonymity and has some mistakes in its formal analysis. To solve this problem, a novel pairing scheme is presented in [145]. Similarly, the protocols in [146] and [147] can address the security issues in [144]. Based on the blockchain, an authentication scheme is presented in [148], which is shown to offer privacy protection and secure storage of medical records. However, its analysis against various attacks is missing. In addition, the blockchains have high storage and computation costs [149]. These performance issues can be addressed by the protocols in [150] and [151]. Similarly, the anonymous three-factor authentication scheme in [152] and password-based authentication protocol in [153] are lightweight and can remedy the issues in [148]. Unfortunately, the protocol in [153] deploys a single shared key between gateway and sensors and hence is insecure. This issue is resolved by the remote authentication and key establishment scheme in [154] and physical layer based device pairing protocol

in [155]. Although the certificateless remote authentication scheme in [156] offers anonymity and resilience against key escrow problems, it cannot withstand replay and man-in-the-middle attacks. These security problems are effectively addressed by the protocol in [157]. However, the blockchains in this scheme makes it unnecessarily extensive [158]. To solve this problem, an energy efficient and secure protocol in [159] can be utilized.

To protect against main-in-the-middle and impersonation attacks, password-based authentication technique is presented in [160], while a stable and effective fuzzy logic based authentication protocol is developed in [161]. Although the scheme in [162] is privacy-preserving, it incurs high processing cost at the hub node. On the other hand, pair-wise and group keys [163] based protocols in [164] are never validated and access to data in storage is not protected. Based on fuzzy vault, an authentication scheme is presented in [165], which is shown to offer resilience against data alteration, brute-force and impersonation. However, this protocol has high computation and communication overheads. This problem can be resolved by the anonymous authentication scheme in [166], which is demonstrated to offer untraceability at low complexities.

3. Results and Discussion

Based on the review in the previous section, numerous shortcomings have been discovered in virtually all the current security techniques. Table 1 presents a summary of the challenges experienced with the current WBAN security solutions.

Table 1 Summary of Challenges in Current Schemes

Scheme	Challenges
Liu et al. [30]	Privacy & security evaluation missing
Nikooghadam & Amintoosi [31]	Cannot uphold user anonymity
Saeed et al. [34]	Not suitable for high mobility and multiple server environments
Islam & Biswas [35]	Susceptible to denial of service attack
Mattias & Abie [42]	Validation is missing
Tan et al. [46]	Security analysis is missing
Zhao et al. [44]	Vulnerable to denial of service attacks, cannot uphold perfect forward secrecy, cannot ensure session key agreement
Wei et al. [57]	incurs extremely high communication costs
Chia-Hui & Chung [62]	Vulnerable to offline password guessing, replay, smart card loss, forgery attacks
Xu et al. [63]	Susceptible to key compromise, replay, privacy leakages, impersonation attacks
Zhang et al. [64]	Lacks protection against Sybil, sink and wormhole attacks
Kumar & Chand [19]	Has key escrow problems
Renuka et al. [66]	Incurs high execution time at the server side
Chang et al. [68]	Lacks security evaluation against adversarial attacks
Wu et al. [69]	Low entropy passwords are vulnerable to brute force and dictionary attacks
Zhang et al. [70]	Is devoid of discussion on security features
Tritilanunt [72]	Lacks analysis of the communication and computation costs
Xiong [79]	Computationally extensive
Wu et al. [82]	High computation , client impersonation attacks
Sahoo et al. [85]	Does not consider untraceability, unlinkability and non-repudiation
Ibrahim et al. [86]	Vulnerable to de-synchronization
Xie et al. [92]	Batch verification is not included

Cao et al. [93]	Cannot offer unlinkability and user anonymity
Wang [95]	Lacks user anonymity and is vulnerable to smart card loss, offline password guessing & credentials leakage attacks
Ullah et al. [97]	Lacks evaluation against security attacks
Jegadeesan et al. [98]	Devoid of discussion on vital security attacks such as man-in-the-middle, impersonation, modification and eavesdropping
Tsai & Lo [99]	Is computationally intensive, vulnerable to impersonation attack and does not offer mutual authentication
Kumar & Saxena [100]	Lacks user anonymity
Amin et al. [103]	Vulnerable to offline guessing attacks
Abina et al. [104]	Susceptible to node compromise attack
Mwitende et al. [105]	Incurs high computation costs, its resilience against security attacks is not provided
Wang & Zhang [107]	Cannot withstand impersonation attacks
Kumari & Om [109]	Vulnerable to user tracking and offline password guessing attacks
Yang et al. [111]	Has challenges in the management of a set of pseudo-IDs
Jiang et al. [116]	Susceptible to replay and spoofing attacks
Wen et al. [117]	Cannot withstand user forgery and offline password guessing attacks
Zhao [119]	Cannot achieve user unlinkability
Li et al. [120]	Can be compromised by malicious group members
Bhawna et al. [122]	Is never evaluated against non-repudiation
Farash et al. [123]	Vulnerable to user tracking attacks
Tan & Chung [125]	Susceptible to denial of service and impersonation attacks
Jiang et al. [126]	Cannot resist session- specific temporary information threats and de-synchronization attacks
Shen et al. [133]	Lacks resilience against key escrow and non-repudiation
Anwar et al. [136]	Is slower and highly complex
Debayan et al. [138]	Lacks security analysis
Wu et al. [140]	Fails to offer forward key secrecy
Liu et al. [142]	Vulnerable to impersonation attack and cannot offer user anonymity
Santanu et al. [144]	It fails to provide anonymity and has some mistakes in its formal analysis
Cheng et al. [148]	Its analysis against various attacks is missing, has high storage and computation costs
Muhammad & Kumari [153]	Deploys a single shared key between gateway and sensors and hence is insecure
Omala et al. [156]	Cannot withstand replay and man-in-the-middle attacks
Bhattacharya et al. [157]	Computationally extensive
Xu et al. [162]	It incurs high processing cost at the hub node
Drira et al. [164]	Data in storage is not protected
Hodgkiss & Djahel [165]	Has high computation and communication overheads

As shown in Table 1 above, these challenges can broadly be classified as being against privacy, security, communication costs, computation overheads, storage complexities, susceptibility to attacks as well as key escrow issues. As such, the recommendations in Section 4 below are thought to be ideal for enhanced WBAN security.

3.1. Recommendations

The messages exchanged in WBANs are sensitive, private and mission-critical. As such, any leakages, corruption or misuse can potentially lead to job losses, humiliation, incorrect medication, mental disturbance, unhealthy relationship or even improper care. As such, security and privacy are essential ingredients of WBAN systems as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Proposed Communication Architecture

As shown in Figure 2, all the transmitted data need to be enciphered using strong encryption algorithms. Although numerous data security [167] schemes have been developed over the recent past, they have been shown to have a number of security and privacy issues. For instance, techniques such as digital signatures, Advanced Encryption Standards (AES), public key infrastructure (PKI) and elliptic curve cryptography point multiplications may be inefficient for the resource limited WBAN devices. Particularly, the management of digital certificates in PKI-based authentication protocols is inefficient [168]. In addition, high computational primitives such as ECC and identity-based bilinear operations [169]-[174] have led to the deployment of lightweight crypto-primitives such as hash functions and XOR functions for the design of more efficient security protocols. Besides performance, communication sessions unlinkability, mutual authentication and anonymity [175] must be upheld in WBAN security frameworks. In this regard, an ideal WBAN security solution must fulfill the following requirements:

- Efficiency –the security schemes must not overburden the WBAN devices in terms of processing power, communication bandwidth and storage requirements.
- Perfect forward secrecy – the adversary who manages to capture the current session key should be unable to correctly derive the session key for the subsequent session.
- User untraceability and anonymity - the attacker eavesdropping the communication channel should be incapable of associating any communication session to a particular communicating entity.
- Mutual authentication – before any access to the sensed data can be granted, the requesting device should be sufficiently validated.
- Revocability – it should be easy to identify and retract any secret tokens or privileges accorded to the communicating entities once they are compromised.
- Resilience against – the security systems should be capable of withstanding typical WBAN attack vectors such as denial of services, man-in-the-middle, de-synchronization, packet replays among others.

A scheme with all of the above requirements offers strong security at low overheads. These are the bare minimum for the success and large scale adoption of the WBANs in the healthcare sector.

4. Conclusion

Wireless body area networks have become part and parcel of the electronic health systems where they facilitate remote monitoring of the patients as well as the elderly. Therefore, massive volumes of sensitive and private data flows between the patients and the hospital medical staff. Since the transmission of the collected data from the patients is over open wireless channels, many attacks are possible. To curb these attacks, numerous security solutions have been presented

in literature. However, this review has identified many security, privacy and performance gaps that need to be filled. As such, a number of recommendations have been presented that can potentially improve on the wireless body networks security posture.

Future work

Future work involves putting these recommendations into practice in form of algorithms that can then be analyzed to showcase their resilience and performance.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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